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Review Article

**RADIATION DOSES IN IMAGING PROCEDURES; A REVIEW
OF RECENT LITERATURE****Ridha Fadhel Albahrani¹, Rizq Abdulrahman Badawi², Mushary Abdullah Alzuhiri³,
Mohammed Hamed Alblowi⁴, Sultan Majdi Alsheikh⁴**¹ Prince Saud Bin Jalawi Hospital² Taibah University³ Imam Muhammad Ibn Saud Islamic University⁴ King Abdulaziz University**Abstract:**

Introduction: X-rays and other imaging modalities are considered to be the hugest human source of radiation exposure in the world. The recent significant development and advances in the field of imaging and interventional radiology is the main cause of this increase in radiation exposure.

Aim of work: In this review, we will discuss several common imaging procedures, their radiation doses, and possible future harms associated with them.

Methodology: We did a systematic search for radiation doses using PubMed and Google Scholar search engines. The terms used in the search were: radiation, doses, diagnostic radiology, and interventional radiology.

Conclusions: The use of radiological imaging has been dramatically increasing lately for uses in both diagnosis and interventions. However, these advances and advantages do not come without disadvantages; radiological imaging is still limited by the radiation exposure which places both patients and physicians in significant risks and harms. Therefore, there has been an effort to decrease and optimize the doses used in radiological procedures in a way that will reduce the risk of developing cancer, but still achieves the high-quality outcomes.

Keywords: radiation dose, diagnostic imaging, x-ray, computed tomography

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INTRODUCTION:

X-rays and other imaging modalities are considered to be the biggest human source of radiation exposure in the world. It has been estimated that the average radiation dose that a person gets a year from medical imaging can reach 3.0 milliSievert, which is equal to doing about one hundred and fifty X-rays to the chest [1]. Earth is also naturally responsible about 2.4 milliSievert radiation exposure for humans. Reports have suggested that up to 40% of the overall radiation exposure that a human gets of radiation could be caused by cardiologists and medical procedures they perform [2]. This relatively high radiation exposure does not only harm the patients, but also the medical staff and healthcare providers. In fact, studies have concluded that the occupational exposure of radiation that a cardiologist can get is more than double the occupational exposure of radiation that a radiologist usually gets. Moreover, these exposure rates have been dramatically increasing lately [3].

The recent significant development and advances in the field of imaging and interventional radiology is the main cause of this increase in radiation exposure. However, despite these advances, practitioners have not been well-aware of the real harm of radiation caused by these techniques. In fact, a report has concluded that most cardiologists and physicians in other specialties usually underestimate the risks associated with radiation, and do not know safe doses that are associated with less harm [4].

The main concern of increasing radiation exposure is its association with higher cancer rates, which is considered to be a huge threat to the public health. In addition, these cases of cancer are usually challenging, unpredictable, and hard to be attributed to radiation itself, because of the relatively long time they take to develop [5]. Therefore, before ordering a radiological test, the benefits and harms should be well studied. Unfortunately, a recent report has claimed that more than 35% of radiological procedures indicated in the cardiology field are unnecessary, and have significant risks that outweigh possible benefits [6]. It is, however, challenging to make the right call, as assessing risks and benefits can be sometimes subjective with the absence of a solid measurement unit. For example, the risk-benefit ratio of doing a test could be favorable in a patient with certain presentation, but not in another patient with the same presentation.

In this review, we will discuss several common imaging procedures, their radiation doses, and possible future harms associated with them.

METHODOLOGY:

We did a systematic search for radiation doses using PubMed search engine (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) and Google Scholar search engine (<https://scholar.google.com>). Our search also looked for imaging procedures. All relevant studies were retrieved and discussed. We only included full articles.

The terms used in the search were: radiation, doses, diagnostic radiology, and interventional radiology. The study was approved by the ethical board of King Abdulaziz University Hospital.

Nuclear medicine: doses and risks

Exposure to radiation in the emergency department was estimated to count for more than 25% of the overall radiation exposure. In addition, it was estimated that of more than half of these procedures were done by cardiologists [7].

To decrease the radiation doses and thus radiation exposure in nuclear imaging procedures, several strategies can be done like using agents as tetrofosmin or sestamibi when performing single-photon emission CT scanning. Another example is the use of other non-radiological investigations in patients who do not have a high pre-test probability for the disease [8].

In the field of cardiology, a recent protocol was suggested to decrease the exposure to radiation by 75%, where all patients undergoing stress test initially, and only patients with positive results undergoing radiological procedures. Unfortunately, not all clinicians follow this protocol due to the absence of awareness about the risks and harms associated with increased radiation exposure risks. This absence of awareness of this issue has also led to the increase of performing dual radioisotope testing procedures, which put patients at an extremely high exposure to radiation (about 30 milliSievert). A new SPECT detector that depends on technologies of cadmium zinc telluride have been developed to decrease the radiation exposure and preserve good quality of images obtained [4].

Computed tomography: doses and risks

The rates of using CT imaging during diagnostic procedures have been significantly increasing over the recent years. In the year 1980, it was estimated that about three million CT images were obtained, whereas in the year 2007 more than seventy million CT images were obtained in the United States alone. Despite this dramatic increase in the use of CT imaging techniques, the doses used in radiation have been decreasing, with a reduction of more than 75% of the dose used. Moreover, there has been a clear

tendency to use measures, protocols, and improved imaging technologies that reduce radiation doses [9].

In the cardiology field, the dose that is used during a coronary CT study is estimated to be about 2-3 milliSievert higher than the dose used in a calcium score study. Due to recent attempts to increase the awareness and solve this issue, manufacturers have been competing with each other to develop more advanced CT techniques that will achieve clear high-quality images, with lower radiation doses. Examples of these emerging imaging techniques in the cardiology field include the use of CT angiography with gated acquisition of a single frame during end-diastole, in patients with slow regular heart rate, which will produce relatively high-quality images with a radiation dose that can be even less than 1 milliSievert [9].

Interventional cardiology and electrophysiology

Fluoroscopically guided diagnostic and interventional procedures have been estimated to be about 12% of radiological procedures performed in cardiology patients. However, alone, they are responsible for about 50% of radiation exposure among these patients¹⁰. To estimate the radiation exposure for a patient following an imaging procedure, it is important also to know the dose-area product associated with this procedure (sometimes called kerma-area product) [11]

This factor is age-related and is known to increase in younger patients [11].

Radiation dose estimates in digital breast tomosynthesis:

Digital breast tomosynthesis (DBT) is an emerging imaging technique that has been used in attempts to increase the accuracy of mammography and provide an appropriate replacement for full-field digital mammography. Recent reports have concluded that the use of digital breast tomosynthesis has been increasing, which correlated with increasing evidence on its accuracy. Therefore, it is essential to study radiation exposure associated with this technique and evaluate potential harms caused by it [12].

Studies found that the use of tomosynthesis solely (either in one view or two views) was associated with radiation exposure that was similar to mammography. However, when combined with mammography, tomosynthesis led to a significant increase in radiation exposure. This was overcome when tomosynthesis was performed in a mediolateral-oblique view, and in combination with mammography in cranio-caudal view, which led to a significant improve in the radiation exposure [13].

Further studies on tomosynthesis and possible protocols that could further decrease radiation exposure. These are important as this technique has been used more often in clinical practice. These new protocols should not be only studies in terms of radiation exposure, but also in term of accuracy related with each radiation dose.

Protection of personnel

It is crucial not only to protect patients against risks associated with radiation exposure, but also to protect healthcare providers as they are in continuous exposure which could potentially place them at higher risk of developing complications. Some studies have estimated that the exposure of healthcare providers in the radiology field can be as high as 5 milliSievert annually. Moreover, this exposure can increase in proportion with more experience and practice in the field [14].

Despite the use of shields and protectors to decrease the exposure of the clinician to radiation, exposure is still present. Therefore, certain protocols and strategies should be used by healthcare providers to reduce their exposure. These strategies include, for example, that the healthcare provider exits the room during conventional CT imaging. Moreover, it is essential to provide sufficient training for clinicians and health-care providers in this field to raise the awareness in this issue, and to train them on how to reduce their exposure to radiation during procedures [15].

CONCLUSIONS:

The use of radiological imaging has been dramatically increasing lately for uses in both diagnosis and interventions. This has been due to the significant advances in these techniques that allowed for the development of sophisticated techniques that changed the face of clinical practice. However, these advances and advantages do not come without disadvantages; radiological imaging is still limited by the radiation exposure which places both patients and physicians in significant risks and harms. The most important concern with high radiation exposure is the development in cancers. Therefore, there has been efforts to decrease and optimize the doses used in radiological procedures in a way that will reduce the risk of developing cancer, but still achieves the high-quality outcomes.

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